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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF INNOVATION
DEVELOPMENT IN THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION****Ekaterina Bykovskaya¹, Gocha Kharchilava¹, Chingis Derbenov², Nadezhda Dorzhdeeva²,
Bova Gorodovikova²**¹Moscow State University of management, Moscow, Russia., ²Kalmyk State university named
after B.B. Gorodovikov, Elista, Russia.**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:**

The article assesses the current state and prospects for the development of innovation activities in the Russian Federation. In particular, an analysis of positive and negative regional level is presented on the example of the Republic of Kalmykia.

Keywords: *Innovation, innovation activity, innovation activity, innovation development, region.*

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INTRODUCTION:

The relevance of research on the issues of improving the efficiency of the domestic economy on the basis of innovative factors has not been lost over the years. One of the central tasks of the national economy is to increase the global competitiveness of a country based on innovative factors. The innovative path of economic development is recognized by state executives of top management, economists and analysts as the most promising and cost-effective direction. The main vector of development of the national economy is based primarily on the fact that innovations make a significant contribution to enhanced intensive reproduction, thereby affecting economic stability and progressiveness in the development of society. In our opinion, the

innovation direction implies intensive and progressive socio-economic development. [5]

Dynamic analysis of the proportion of organizations involved in technological, organizational, marketing innovations in the total number of organizations reviewed in the Russian Federation for 2012–2017. showed that the peak of innovation activity fell in 2013, when the value of this indicator was 10.4%. Subsequently, there was a decrease to 9.3% (Figure 1) [3].

In this regard, the decline in innovation activity has led to a decrease in the share of innovative products, works and services. This indicator had a growth trend from 2012 (4.8%) to 2015 (9.2%), but in 2017 it decreased to the level of 8.4%. [3]

Fig. 1. Innovative activity of organizations

In practice, economic and statistical research innovation activity needs to be studied in the context of organizations engaged in technological, organizational, marketing and environmental innovation.

According to Rosstat, it can be concluded that the proportion of organizations engaged in technological

innovation for the period analyzed was higher than the proportion of organizations with organizational, marketing and environmental innovations and averaged 8.7%. Organizations engaged in marketing innovations accounted for 1.8% in 2017, organizational innovations - 2.7%, environmental innovations - 1.6% of the total number of surveyed organizations (Figure 2). [3]

Fig. 2. The share of organizations implementing marketing, organizational, environmental, technological innovations

A decrease in innovation activity can be attributed to a number of factors that have a negative impact on the innovation sphere of the Russian Federation: [3]

1. Insufficient financing of innovation activities. The rating of national expenditures on R & D showed that in 2016 Russia occupied the 28th place. From 2012 to 2016, the cost of technological innovation increased by 3 times, but in 2017 this figure decreased by 0.05% compared with the previous period. This may be due to the crisis in the economy of the Russian Federation. Despite the increase in the cost of technological innovation, the innovative activity of organizations has declined dramatically. This is the result of a decline in investment in the innovation field, due to the fact that investors do not want to risk investing money in high-tech manufacturing and technology.

2. Russia is characterized by a low level of realization of scientific and technical potential and the use of knowledge for socio-economic development. Thus, the knowledge index, which characterizes the country's potential in relation to the knowledge economy, in 2015 allowed the country to occupy only 44th place.

3. There is a decrease in the number of qualified personnel engaged in research and development work. Over the past 10 years, this figure fell by 9.1%. This is due to the migration abroad of domestic scientists, inventors and researchers.

The Agency for Strategic Initiatives, which has created a new model of the system of additional education - the children's technopark "Kvantorium", partially took up the solution of the problem of the lack of qualified engineering personnel and scientists.

The project is being implemented to identify and develop talent in children in such areas as neurobiology, biotechnology, applied cosmonautics, promising vehicles, etc., which will enable them to enter the labor market with highly qualified scientific personnel in the future. This project involves the participation of the Republic of Tatarstan, Altai Territory, Moscow Region, Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Area. By 2020, the country plans to operate at least 10 Kvantoriumov. [2]

Also significant efforts are aimed at stimulating research and innovative development in higher education. Financial support was provided to innovative programs for 57 universities. On a competitive basis, 29 universities were given the status of national research universities and funds were allocated for the implementation of development programs, including the creation of innovative infrastructure and the development of research activities. Measures are being taken to attract world-famous scientists to research activities in Russian universities, as well as to support the cooperation of universities with organizations and the further development of the innovative infrastructure of universities.

Since 2017 was declared the Year of Ecology in the Russian Federation, the introduction of environmental innovations was carried out in such areas as environmental protection, improving the collection, sorting and deep processing of household and industrial waste, safe disposal of especially hazardous waste, wastewater treatment, plant and animal world and their habitat. [four]

In general, it is not possible to reverse a number of

negative trends that are important for innovation, significantly accelerate the process of integrating the Russian innovation system into the global system and dramatically increase the innovation activity and efficiency of companies, including state ones, and create a competitive environment that would encourage the use of innovation.

In order to solve existing problems and bring the Russian innovation sphere to a qualitatively new level of development, it is necessary to expand and improve the methodology of state regulation of innovation activities. For its development, first of all, it is necessary to increase the efficiency of public spending on scientific and innovative research, since at present funding is allocated without due regard for work results. [7]

Since the innovation activity of the country also depends on the innovation activity of the regions and enterprises, in order to eliminate the identified problems and its further innovative development, it is

advisable to consider the innovation activity in a particular region and in a particular enterprise.

As can be seen from table 1, the Republic of Kalmykia by such indicators as the innovative activity of organizations and the number of personnel engaged in research and development ranks last among the regions of the Southern Federal District, which can be attributed to a low population. In spite of this, innovative activity in the republic is still developing, since the Republic of Kalmykia occupies a leading position in the number of developed advanced production technologies. Also, despite the low level, the growth of domestic current expenditures on applied research and development has increased in recent years in the Republic.

These data confirm the fact that at present there is a need to create a technological platform that consolidates the efforts of the authorities, scientific and educational and business communities for the formation of state policy in the field of innovation.

Table 1: Main indicators of innovation activity by Southern Federal District regions in 2017 [6]

Region	The number of personnel engaged in research and development, people.	Domestic expenditures for research and development, billion rubles	Number of advanced manufacturing technologies developed	The number of used advanced production technologies	Innovative activity of organizations, percent
Southern Federal District	28011	25,8	76	12308	7,1
Republic of Adygea	282	0,2	-	230	4,2
Republic of Kalmykia	184	0,1	31	85	2,0
Republic of Crimea	2096	1,4	-	102	2,8
Krasnodar region	7532	5,9	16	5163	9,1
Astrakhan region	692	0,5	4	587	9,1
Volgograd region	4026	3,5	-	2511	4,9
Rostov region	12102	13,7	25	3314	8,4
Sevastopol	1097	0,7	-	316	3,3

Today, one of these sites has become the Coordination Council for the Development of Innovation Activities under the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Its main goal is the organization of regional state policy in the field of scientific innovation, ensuring the interaction of scientific organizations, government bodies of the republic in matters of ensuring the investment attractiveness of the region. It is obvious that young and enterprising scientists, entrepreneurs, farmers from the center of youth innovation creativity will eventually join this public organization. [1]

One of the most important tasks facing the regional economy today is the need to increase the susceptibility of importing economies and innovations, and launch a self-replicating demand for innovations. The work of the Ministry of Economy and Trade of the Republic on state support of small and medium-sized businesses contributes to the solution of this problem. For several years, entrepreneurs engaged in innovative activities have been supported. Subsidies are made in various directions and for various purposes. On the one hand, state support for small businesses in the form of subsidies is aimed at those who plan to open their

business, on the other, at those who are modernizing their production. Thus, in 2017, six small innovative enterprises of individual entrepreneurs operating in the framework of innovation activities were subsidized. This is, first of all, OOO NPP KUUZIKU, engaged in the development of the economic base in the southern territory, and OOO NPP Aquarius, engaged in the reduction of production of enterprises and objects of the environment through water treatment.

The republican register of investment projects eligible for grant support included activities of the innovation center for the cultivation, processing and sale of triticale grain flour in a high baking format of the individual entrepreneur Vladimir Nostaev. Its activity has been carried out in the republic since 2013, the developed business project is designed for the annual production and sale of two thousand tons of flour. This project in 2015 became the winner of the competition "100 best goods of Russia", as well as the winner of the competition in the nominations "Foodstuffs" and "Novelty of the Year".

An important component of the innovative development of the region is to reduce costs and improve the quality of agricultural products through the introduction of innovative scientific technologies. Therefore, the development of the agro-industrial complex should be defined as the main sectoral priority of the innovative development of the regional economy. In this regard, another innovative project is currently being completed - a meat processing complex for fattening, slaughter and primary processing of livestock, which includes a production trade and logistics center and a complex for processing leather ecologically clean raw materials with a capacity of 15-20 thousand tons per year. The implementation of this project will give a powerful impetus to the development of villages, an increase in agricultural production. On its basis, it is planned to organize a territorial meat complex for the production and processing of complex farms.

In 2017, a center for youth innovation creativity was created in Kalmykia, which became a link in the innovation infrastructure. The new structure is focused on creating favorable conditions for young people and small and medium-sized businesses in order to engage them in the scientific, technical and innovative areas. [11]

The modern center of science and education in the Republic of Kalmykia is Kalmyk State University, which has the necessary resources - specialists, experience, material and scientific base, able to

become an organizational catalyst for achieving the goal of innovative development of the republic. [8] To date, elements of the innovation infrastructure and small innovative business have been created on the basis of KalmGU based on the support of scientific research, which include training and production and educational centers, youth innovation and technology centers, small innovative enterprises, and an innovation and analytical department. So, 19 educational and industrial and educational centers are engaged in research in the field of immunogenetic research of animals, the study of problems of physical culture and sports, the organization and conduct of foreign language courses, etc. The research results obtained at the sites of six youth innovation and technology centers (nanotechnologies and energy efficient systems, 3D prototyping, exhibition, intellectual property, etc.), served as the basis for the creation of 14 small innovative enterprises. [10]

An important role in attracting young people to research, discovering and realizing their potential is played by the UMNİK Club - an association of young scientists and students to participate in the development of innovative processes in the republic. They receive support from the Foundation for the Promotion of the Development of Small Enterprises in the Scientific and Technical Sphere. To date, 78 out of 140 developed projects of young scientists of KalmSU have received the support of this Foundation under the UMNİK program. Applications for obtaining copyright certificates and patents for innovative developments are being actively applied. [9]

CONCLUSION:

Thus, the transition of the economy of the Republic of Kalmykia to the innovative way of development involves technological renewal of production, increasing the competitiveness of products manufactured in the republic, increasing its export potential, and turning intellectual resources into a real economic factor. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve a number of tasks: increase the number of innovatively active organizations; to increase the volume of innovative products produced in the region competitive in the Russian and world markets; integrate scientific, educational and technological potentials to solve the most pressing problems of the production complex; develop innovative infrastructure.

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